

APPLYING THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN AGRICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

The largest sector of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is agriculture. First of all, it serves to meet the demand of the population for food. In this regard, the agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan has made great strides. The republic's agriculture produces almost the bulk of foodstuffs in sufficient quantities for our population. Agriculture provides industry with raw materials. Today, more than 60% of the fiber used in the country's light and textile industries is domestically produced cotton fiber.

Introduction

It is known that agricultural production is often associated with land. The relationship between land ownership, management and use and development is called agrarian relations.

The peculiarity of agricultural production is that here the laws of nature are directly related to economic laws, because agricultural production is directly related to living things - land, plants, livestock. Here the land is the object of labor and the main means of production, the object of economic management, it does not wear out, it is not eaten, and if it is treated well, its productivity will be good.

The basis of the agro-industrial complex is agriculture. All sectors of the agro-industrial complex are connected with agriculture. Some of them produce and supply means of production for agriculture, while others prepare, process

and deliver agricultural products to consumers. Many industries provide services for the smooth operation of these networks.

All means of production used in agriculture can be private, private, or collective. At present, the main forms of farming in agriculture are in the form of farmers and peasants, whose production processes are based on the use of different climatic and soil conditions.

All the means of production available in agriculture (tractors, machines, vehicles, buildings, structures, perennial trees, productive livestock and working animals) constitute the capital structure. Working capital includes: young and domestic animals, fodder, seed stocks, chemical fertilizers, various means of production with a service life of less than one year - inverters, fuel and lubricants. 'ladi. Capital circulates, that is, from the form of money

to the form of production, from it to the form of commodity, and back to the form of money.

In agriculture, production time is long and working hours are determined by days. In agriculture, the production process is seasonal. Combines, for example, use a variety of planting tools in a short time. Given the relative density of the population and the limited availability of agricultural land, private ownership of land will be introduced, with state ownership remaining.

METHOD AND RECOMMENDATION

Agriculture, which is the basis of the agro-industrial complex, has its own characteristics. These features distinguish agriculture from other industries and set their own requirements for the organization of production. These features include:

1. The impact of natural factors in agriculture is great. They stem from the seasonality of production. This requires taking into account the efficient use of available resources throughout the year in the organization of production. The temporary inactivity of the population during the winter months causes some social problems. These issues pose a number of challenges for scientists, experts and business people.

2. Living organisms are involved in agriculture as a means of production. This, in turn, requires professionals to know not only the laws of economics, but also the laws of biology, and to take them into account in the organization of production. The efficiency of agricultural labor depends

to a large extent on the biological potential of plants and livestock.

3. Land is the main means of production and has its own characteristics of use. Denying them or ignoring them enough can lead to major negative consequences.

4. There is a big difference between the period of material expenditures in agriculture and the period of receipt of income from activities. In other words, only expenses are incurred throughout the year. This is due to the fact that the costs of preparing the land for planting, the purchase and consumption of seeds, fertilizers, fuel and lubricants, labor costs are paid on a monthly basis. The crop ripens in a certain period. The crop is sold and then cash comes in. Of course, in practice, there may be a certain amount of cash flow as a result of advances to agricultural enterprises on the basis of contracts, the use of loans or the organization of certain services. However, in general, the fact that expenses are spent during the year, and revenues fall only in certain periods, creates its own objective requirements. Agrarian policy should be guided by this feature.

5. Agricultural production is carried out on very large areas. This, in turn, creates certain requirements for production, location of settlements, which must be taken into account in the formation of the material and technical base of agriculture.

6. It consumes a part of agricultural products as seeds, fodder, food.

7. Many types of agricultural products can not be stored for a long time. This problem is exacerbated by the fact that agricultural products ripen almost

simultaneously. This, in turn, requires that the organizations engaged in the production and processing of agricultural products work tirelessly, and in some periods have a very large capacity. In the rest of the year, these forces are relatively idle. This situation requires large warehouses for processing industries. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the cost of the product.

Of course, an in-depth study of such peculiarities and the organization of production with constant consideration will ensure the effective functioning of agriculture. Undoubtedly, with the development of science and technology, the impact of these features of agriculture is relatively small, but not completely eliminated.

Agriculture is one of the largest sectors of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Today, the role of agriculture in the country's economy is very large. This sector accounts for 26-30% of the country's GDP. In 2020, 26.8% of the country's GDP was generated in this sector. More than half of the hard-earned foreign exchange earnings necessary for the economy of our country comes from the export of products of this sector. More than 60% of the population lives in rural areas. The living standards of our people, the employment of a large part of human resources depend on agriculture. Today, more than 28% of the labor force employed in the economy is engaged in agriculture and forestry. That is why the attention to agriculture, especially in the post-independence years, is rightly growing.

The role of agriculture in the national economy

No	Indicators	2010	2012	2014	2018	2020
1.	Share of gross agricultural output in the country's GDP,%	30,4	30	30,6	28,6	26,8
2.	Growth rate of gross agricultural output,%	103,2	104,5	106,1	107,3	110,1
3.	The share of cotton fiber and food products in total exports,%	32,9	25,9	25,9	22,5	21,9
4.	Share of agricultural labor resources,%	29,7	29,6	29,1	28,3	28,4

According to the table, agriculture is the largest sector of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and its share is declining from year to year. In this regard, it should be noted that in 2010-2020 there was a steady decline in agriculture. The share of agriculture in the country's economy has decreased only due to the relatively rapid development of industry

and services. This is a very positive process. As the country's economy grows rapidly, the share of agriculture in it will decrease. As a result, we will become a country with a developed industry and developed services.

The success of economic and social reforms in the country largely depends on the level of agricultural development. Because

agriculture is an area of political, economic and social significance for our country, it performs the following functions:

- forms the food fund of our country;
- ensures the independence of our country in the field of food;
- supplies raw materials for the processing industry of agricultural products;
- Provides jobs for the population.

The agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan consists of crop and livestock sectors. The crop sector includes cotton, cereals (mainly wheat), potatoes, vegetables, melons, tobacco, fodder crops,

vegetable oilseeds (molasses, sunflower), horticulture and viticulture. . In animal husbandry, cattle breeding, sheep and goat breeding, poultry farming, horse breeding (horse breeding), rabbit breeding, camel breeding, and pig breeding have been formed and developed. In addition, silkworm breeding, beekeeping and fishing are well developed in the country's agriculture. At present, 6.2 mln. head of cattle, 11.1 mln. There are head sheep and goats.

Land fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its distribution by users

№	Ground users	1996 йил		20010йил		2018 йил	
		минг га	%	минг га	%	минг га	%
	Total land fund That's it	44405,0	100,0	44405,0	100,0	44410,3	100,0
1.	Lands used by agricultural enterprises	25317,8	57,0	25112,6	56,6	24819,4	55,8
2.	Lands of forestry enterprises	8695,5	19,7	8446,3	19,1	8402,6	18,9
3.	Lands of industry, transport, defense, communications and other organizations	1868,9	4,2	1926,3	4,4	2264,3	5,2
4.	Residential areas	226,4	0,5	231,2	0,5	238,7	0,5
5.	Reserve land	7492,1	16,8	7472,5	16,8	7432,8	16,7
6.	Lands of hydraulic engineering and other water management organizations	793,8	1,7	804,6	1,8	822,4	1,8
7.	Lands of nature protection, health and cultural significance	10,5	0,02	70,8	0,1	74,3	0,1
8.	Other lands	-	-	340,7	0,7	430,1	0,9

The table shows that in 2018, the bulk of the Republic's land fund, 55.8%, was allocated to the agricultural sector. If we take into account the fact that the forestry, partly hydraulic and other water

management organizations (although small amounts of agricultural products) and some farms under the Ministry of Defense also produce agricultural products, the

above it can be understood that the figure occupies a much larger share.

As of January 2018, there are more than 3,691 hectares of irrigated land, more than 230,000 hectares of orchards and vineyards.

During the years of independence, the structure of agricultural production in the country has changed dramatically. Due to today's demand, land resources involved in agricultural production are allocated mainly for cotton and grain crops.

CONCLUSION

A video conference chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on July 31 on the issues of accelerating the development of cotton, replanting of vacant lands, efficient use of public lands and export of agricultural products meeting was held.

As you know, in a video conference held on July 4 this year, from July 5 to September 5 was announced "Current two months of harvest." The meeting provided a detailed analysis of the work done in this regard.

It was noted that the delay in the development of cotton has not been eliminated in the past, and the development of cotton is still 8-10 days behind, and in some places 12-15 days behind. During the same period last year, an average of 5-7 pods were formed per bush, today it is no more than 3-5.

The main reason for this is that in June-July, local governors and sector leaders, especially farmers, abandoned cotton cultivation under the pretext of harvesting and replanting. said the head of state. The inter-row cultivation and efficient use of water are not well organized. Studies have shown that most

fields do not have cultivators, watermen or workers. In some districts, cotton has even been abandoned. In many areas, cotton is thirsty, leading to crop losses.

According to the Republican working groups, the cultivation of inter-row cotton does not meet the requirements at all. In some areas, due to the involvement of tractors in other activities, cultivation has been delayed, and the gaps between the rows of cotton have reached the point of cracking. Due to the lack of conditions in the "houses of mechanizers", the "squad" and "naryad" systems do not work, 45-50% of cultivators are not used enough.

Four sector leaders in Zarbdor, Guzar, Baghdad and Uychi districts have been ordered to be fired for failing to perform their duties in agriculture.

It was noted that it is necessary to conduct timely and high-quality agro-technical measures on cotton fields, to work between rows without thirst, and to use cultivators effectively.

Unfavorable weather this year has led to an increase in cotton pests and insects. Scientists have found that the survival rate of caterpillars is 76%. This is the highest figure in recent years. In fact, reaching 50 percent of that number is considered an emergency. This year, the number of insects is 1.5 times higher. This problem requires systematic oversight by every responsible manager, especially farmers, to strengthen their personal responsibility.

Scientists predict the spread of spiders on 460,000 hectares, caterpillars on 390,000 hectares and alfalfa on 42,000 hectares this year. Therefore, 127 scientists headed by the heads of research institutes of the Academy of Sciences and the Tashkent State Agrarian University were sent to the

regions. An additional 100 billion soums has been allocated from the budget to protect cotton from pests and insects. But some sector leaders are still indifferent. Thousands of hectares have been chemically treated, but in practice the expected results have not been achieved. That is, the processing is of poor quality and transferred to the name. As a result, in some areas, caterpillars have damaged 4,000 to 5,000 hectares of cotton. Another 8,000-10,000 hectares are at risk.

Improper irrigation also has a negative impact on the development of cotton. Sector leaders and water officials are not doing enough to ensure a fair distribution of water. For example, 50-60%

of the water supplied to a particular district is used for irrigation of secondary and horticultural crops. Due to improper use of water, insufficient water supply and lack of night irrigation, 10-15% of cotton fields in some districts are thirsty. In some districts, 60-65% of the area is irrigated, despite a clear mandate to irrigate cotton by juice. In this regard, the Ministry of Water Resources and the State Veterinary Committee have been tasked with attaching staff from their own systems to farms to produce local fertilizers and irrigate cotton with juice. Measures will be taken against sector leaders and farmers who use water inefficiently.

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